

FRIDGE: Federated Research Infrastructure by Data Governance Extension

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FRIDGE: Federated Research Infrastructure by Data Governance Extension

Project report

1. Project Overview

1.1. Executive Summary

FRIDGE has developed a “satellite TRE” approach for safely using supercomputers as part of a Trusted Research Environment (TRE). This extends the information governance and data security controls of an existing TRE to an isolated part of a supercomputer, allowing it to be safely used for research with sensitive data. FRIDGE takes a shared responsibility model, defining what the supercomputer administrators need to do to isolate a part of their system as a secure “TRE tenancy”. Control of this tenancy is then handed over to the TRE operator, who deploys components of their TRE within it and manages these under the same controls as the rest of their TRE. Researchers using the TRE are then able to safely use the supercomputer’s specialist computer processors within this tenancy for their research with sensitive data.

Enabling the safe use of supercomputers for sensitive data is important because we have a large wealth of health data in the UK, and artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to enable research using this data that could have a huge positive impact improving the quality of our health and healthcare treatment. However, this data is highly sensitive and can therefore only be used for research under strong data security and information governance controls. The government has made a big investment in large AI supercomputers such as AIRR (the AI Research Resource), which can be used for AI-driven research on large datasets. However, these supercomputers were not originally built to provide the level of data security and information governance required for research with sensitive data. Enabling safe research on sensitive data using these AI supercomputers has the potential to give insights that can improve all our health and wellbeing.

In this Early Adopter project, we have shown that the FRIDGE satellite TRE approach works by extending the information governance and data security controls of the Alan Turing Institute’s TRE to securely isolated parts of the two AI Research Resource supercomputers. There is still significant work to do to further develop FRIDGE from this initial proof-of-concept demonstration into something that can be deployed at scale in production. However, we have shown that both the technical approach and the shared responsibility information governance model work in a realistic setting across real-world TREs and supercomputers.

The FRIDGE team worked closely with the core TRevolution teams to ensure that we were developing components that integrated well with the wider set of TRE components they were developing. The FRIDGE satellite TRE approach has been designed to be compliant with the SATRE TRE standard, and we fed into the requirements and design for several of the other TRevolution components where we were solving similar problems, including DIRECTOR for securely connecting federated systems, Five Safes TES for describing and communicating research workloads between systems, and K8TRE for the design of the secure TRE tenancy that TRE components are deployed into.

1.2. The challenge

Modern AI-driven research can generate incredible insights from large data sets. However, this research often requires large numbers of specialised computer processors known as GPUs (Graphical Processing Units), and the UK has recently invested in large AI-enabled supercomputers such as the AIRR AI Research Resource to support researchers in applying AI-driven methods to large data sets.

However, research in areas such as healthcare often uses sensitive data that requires careful handling to maintain its safety and security. Trusted Research Environments (TREs) have been developed as a standard approach for providing secure analysis environments for working safely with sensitive data, limiting access to data only to approved researchers working on approved projects. However, the supercomputers that can provide the large numbers of specialist GPUs needed for modern AI-driven research do not generally provide the level of data security and protection required for working safely with sensitive data, and TREs generally don't provide the large numbers of GPUs needed to support AI-driven research with large data sets.

Supercomputers aren't TREs

Different projects a supercomputer are **not strongly isolated from each other** in the same way as in a TRE.

TREs aren't supercomputers

TREs provide a **small number of strongly isolated computers per project** with few or no AI-capable GPUs.

1.3. The FRIDGE satellite TRE approach

1.3.1. Overview

FRIDGE takes a shared responsibility approach to enabling the safe use of large AI supercomputers for research with sensitive data. The supercomputer operator is responsible for securely isolating part of the supercomputer as a secure "TRE tenancy", cutting the computers within this tenancy off from the rest of the computers in the system. They then hand over control of this tenancy to the TRE operator, who configures the computers within it to be part of their TRE. This involves adding additional layers of security controlling how these computers can communicate with each other and how data is stored on the supercomputer system, and deploying components to allow research workloads to be run on the AI-enabled GPUs within the supercomputer tenancy. The TRE operator connects the TRE tenancy on the supercomputer to their existing TRE via a secure tunnel, ensuring that computers within the tenancy can only be communicated with from their TRE. The supercomputer administrator can create multiple different isolated TRE tenancies, giving control of each tenancy to a different TRE operator. Each TRE operator can manage their tenancy under their own information governance and data security controls.

The TRE administrator isolates part of the supercomputer as a secure TRE tenancy, handing control to the TRE administrator, who configures it as part of their TRE

Multiple TRE tenancies can be configured, each part of a different TRE, controlled by a different TRE operator, under different information governance rules

1.3.2. Governance model

The FRIDGE satellite TRE model recognises that information governance lies at the heart of the challenge of federating systems together to work with sensitive data. For TREs, federating across different governance models has proved extremely challenging, and solving this general challenge lies at the core of the TRevolution programme. FRIDGE tackles the smaller problem of federating one TRE with one supercomputer that is not itself a TRE. In this case, the constraints of the TRE’s governance model are generally stricter than those of the supercomputer and we can take the approach of extending the TRE’s existing information governance regime to a part of the supercomputer to create a “satellite TRE”. In practice, this is achieved through a [shared responsibility model](#), with two key roles sharing the responsibility for securing the satellite TRE.

- The **FRIDGE Hosting Organisation** operates the physical hosting environment for the satellite TRE and is responsible for strongly isolating part of the system to provide a secure “TRE tenancy”. Control of this TRE tenancy is then passed over to the **TRE Operator Organisation**. In the FRIDGE proof-of-concept use case, the **FRIDGE Hosting Organisation** is one of the AIRR supercomputer operator teams at Bristol (for Isambard-AI) or Cambridge (for Dawn).
- The **TRE Operator Organisation** operate the existing TRE that is being extended onto the supercomputer. They take over control of the TRE tenancy from the **FRIDGE Hosting Organisation**, further securing the TRE tenancy and deploying a minimal set of workload management components that allow AI workloads to be sent from their existing TRE to run within the secure TRE tenancy established on the supercomputer. In the FRIDGE proof-of-concept use case Turing is the **TRE Operator Organisation**.

In the originally envisaged implementation of the FRIDGE shared responsibility model, we planned to define a standard shared hosting agreement that could be used across many different **TRE Operator Organisations** and **FRIDGE Hosting Organisations**. This would outline the responsibilities each of the two organisation in securing and operating the satellite TRE as a set of common high-level commitments. A site-specific technical appendix would detail how each **FRIDGE Hosting Organisation** assured this in practice, with this audited as part of any existing audited security accreditation they hold. However, in the FRIDGE proof-of-concept use

case, the computational resources on the AIRR supercomputers are managed by DSIT rather than the individual supercomputer hosting organisations. This has introduced additional complexity, requiring the team to work with DSIT to integrate the shared responsibility model into their AIRR allocation process, introducing a new **Resource Allocator** role. We are continuing this work as we further develop the FRIDGE model from proof-of-concept to a production-ready implementation and are scoping a pilot TRE call for AIRR with DSIT.

In the FRIDGE proof-of-concept implementation, the **FRIDGE Hosting Organisation** also deploys a Kubernetes cluster within the TRE tenancy to provide a common standardised infrastructure layer for deployment of satellite TRE components. However, this could also be deployed by the **TRE Operator Organisation** if the **FRIDGE Hosting Organisation's** systems permitted them to be safely granted sufficient privileges to do so. The combination of the TRE tenancy security model and its common Kubernetes-based infrastructure layer has been co-designed with the K8TRE team, and the eventual goal is for the same TRE tenancy to be able to support deployment of any TRevolution component within it, whether within a FRIDGE satellite TRE or a K8TRE “full stack” TRE.

Further details of the FRIDGE governance model and the concepts and roles within it can be found in our [governance report](#) and will be kept up to date as they evolve in the [FRIDGE documentation](#).

1.3.3. Technical approach

FRIDGE is designed to enable an existing TRE to harness the capabilities of AI supercomputers, functioning as a “satellite TRE”. As such, our goal was to find the most efficient way of allowing the users of those existing TREs to run AI workloads transparently from within their own TRE, while maintaining appropriate security controls at all times.

First, we had to define a secure “TRE tenancy” for our target supercomputer platforms – Dawn and Isambard AI – to isolate the sensitive data and workloads from the rest of the supercomputer infrastructure, as well as the outside world. Because each platform had quite different technical constraints, we created a technical specification that could be implemented across both sites, while also defining the TRE tenancy using infrastructure-as-code.

Second, we needed to define the FRIDGE service that would run within that TRE tenancy. We chose Kubernetes as the core technology for our FRIDGE service. Kubernetes is a framework for providing a common infrastructure layer across different computing platforms. As it is platform-agnostic, highly portable, and a core element of many of the TRevolution projects, it was an excellent fit for our need for a transferable technical solution. The FRIDGE service was designed to allow, via a secure tunnel from the home TRE, users to upload data, run AI workloads using that data, and return the results to their home TRE.

A key principle throughout was *defence in depth*: multiple, independent levels of security ensuring that a breach at one level is never sufficient to compromise the security of the data. With the *shared-responsibility* model in mind, we designed the tenancy and FRIDGE services to be deployed by the hosting organisation and the home TRE administrators respectively. The hosting organisation holds the keys to the tenancy itself, while the home TRE administrators hold the keys for FRIDGE, including keys for encrypting data at rest.

The supercomputer administrators set up external controls over network traffic in and out of the FRIDGE TRE tenancy. Within the FRIDGE tenancy, we use multiple additional security methods, such as network restrictions and role-based access control. Should those be breached and a bad actor gain control of the

FRIDGE, they would need to separately find a way to lift the infrastructure-level controls that define the TRE tenancy to be able to extract data.

Together, these elements defined a secure and portable architecture for extending TRE governance to AI supercomputers, enabling existing TREs to extend their capabilities safely and securely.

1.4. Integrating with TRevolution

The FRIDGE team worked closely with the SATRE and K8TRE teams and also fed into the work of the DIRECTOR and Five Safes TES teams. We worked with SATRE both to ensure that a TRE with a FRIDGE satellite deployed on a supercomputer constitutes a SATRE-compliant TRE, and to inform the design of SATRE's new federation pillar. We also worked closely with the K8TRE team on the design of the TRE tenancy that provides a securely isolated area of the underlying infrastructure to deploy TRE components into, with a common Kubernetes infrastructure layer to support cross-platform deployment. We also fed requirements into the design of the DIRECTOR mesh networking for securely connecting different systems within a TRE federation, and the Five Safes TES standard for describing and exchanging workloads to be run across these federated systems. When developing components for secure inter-TRE networking and workload management, we kept the work of these two strands in mind to ensure that we were maintaining the same responsibility boundaries between components and to avoid duplication of effort. More broadly, we contributed to building a cluster of expertise across DARE projects in building tools for trusted research on Kubernetes, through regular tech integration meetings and workshops. This knowledge sharing had a force-multiplying effect upon development and a longer-term vision of an ecosystem of modular TRevolution components, where TRE operators can deploy and combine DARE products to suite their needs. More details on how we worked with the core TRevolution team are outlined in section 2.

1.5. Outputs and outcomes

1.5.1. Technical proof of concept “satellite TRE” design and implementation

Open code and guidance on how to create a secure satellite TRE on the AIRR supercomputers. All elements of the proof-of-concept implementation are publicly available on the [FRIDGE GitHub repository](#) under an open-source BSD-3 licence. This contains:

- Infrastructure-as-code defining a TRE tenancy on Turing's cloud and the Dawn supercomputer
- Infrastructure-as-code defining a FRIDGE satellite TRE to be deployed within a TRE tenancy
- FRIDGE API service for TRE users to send workload to the FRIDGE satellite TRE

1.5.2. A shared responsibility model for extending TRE governance to a supercomputer

A shared governance model setting out what the supercomputer administrators and the TRE operators need to do in order to secure a section of the supercomputer as part of a TRE. This model is published as part of the [FRIDGE documentation](#), and discussed further in our [governance report](#).

1.5.3. Validation of approach on AIRR supercomputers

Demonstrated an example AI research workload with non-sensitive data to evaluate the functionality and security of the FRIDGE satellite TRE approach across a real-world TRE and supercomputer, proving the

viability of satellite TRE model. Demonstrated shared responsibility in action, with a non-sensitive workload between motivated contributors. See our [workflow validation report](#) for more details.

1.5.4. Public involvement and engagement

Public involvement and engagement was tightly integrated into our project structure. Our PIE lead was a first-class member of the project leadership team and formal co-investigator and our principal investigator was our PIE co-lead. Our PIE activity fell broadly into two streams – project focussed activity and engagement with the activities of the wider DARE PIE workstream.

Our project focussed PIE activity began with our PIE lead upskilling the wider project team on how to embed the public perspective into their day to day thinking and to effectively engage with the public at PIE events. While we originally planned to leverage the PIE groups from the TREvolution workstream and the health project we were working with at Turing, we later established a project focussed TRE Public Advisory Group at Turing, as we realised we needed deeper and more regular input from the public to steer our work. This group is made up of 10 public members from a diversity of backgrounds who meet with the project team monthly, and they will continue to work with us on other related work to guide our decisions and ensure we are explaining our work effectively to the public.

We augmented our project focussed PIE group with attendance at many of the DARE Collaboration Cafes, working with the organisers to ensure key questions for FRIDGE were integrated into these discussions and to support discussion of topics of common concern across FRIDGE and other projects. We also ran a dedicated FRIDGE Collaboration Café to validate our approach with and gather input from a wider range of public participants. Finally, we participated in one of the DARE UK AI Dialogue workshops, providing an opportunity to explore wider concerns around AI with under-represented communities. More details of our PIE activity can be found in section 4.

1.5.5. Engagement with other stakeholder communities

In addition to the public, we engaged with more focussed stakeholder communities, including the wider TRE community, the supercomputing community and the research software engineering community. This engagement was primarily through joining these communities at their events to present and discuss our work and get their feedback. We outline key engagements below.

TRE community

- Apr 2025: Secure Data Infrastructure Leader's Forum
- Jul 2025: NHS Secure Data Environment technical working group meeting
- Sep 2025: TRE Community conference 2025
- Dec 2025: Challenges and enablers of HPC for healthcare workshop
- Jan 2026: NHS Secure Data Environment technical working group meeting

Supercomputing community

- Mar 2025: NFCS National Federated Compute Systems NetworkPlus day 2025
- May 2025: HPC-SIG - High-Performance Computing Special Interest Group meeting
- Feb 2026: NFCS National Federated Compute Systems Spring Conference 2026
- Mar 2026: Isambard Summit 2026

Research software engineering community

- Jul 2025: STEP-UP RSLondon 2025 - Research software engineering regional conference
- Sep 2025: RSECon25 - Research software engineering national conference

2. Working with TRevolution

2.1. SATRE

We collaborated closely with SATRE through the development of the SATRE federation pillar, and the design of FRIDGE governance documentation. Our goal was to ensure that a FRIDGE instance, connected to an existing TRE constitutes a SATRE-compliant, federated TRE.

One of our team members, a governance and architecture expert, worked across FRIDGE and SATRE providing oversight. Furthermore, we contributed to the development of the SATRE federation pillar through weekly SATRE meetings and collaboration cafés.

The outcome of this collaboration is a consistent pair of governance documents, the [FRIDGE governance documentation](#) and SATRE 2.0 draft specification.

2.2. K8TRE and DIRECTOR

Both FRIDGE and K8TRE aimed to build TREs based on Kubernetes, a cross-platform infrastructure layer available on a wide range of cloud and on-premise computer systems. We took advantage of this to share knowledge and experiences and avoid duplicating effort. We communicated through attending regular TRevolution tech synchronisation meetings, and at longer workshop days.

Establishing this connection helped ensure each of K8TRE and FRIDGE have clear and distinct purposes. With K8TRE being a “full-stack” TRE including all components necessary to conduct trusted research, while FRIDGE is a minimal, satellite TRE which extends an existing TRE to a “satellite” TRE tenancy on a third-party compute provider.

Learnings from the unique security and governance challenges in FRIDGE helped to better understand how to secure Kubernetes for TREs and to harden the K8TRE environment. In particular, the use of Pod Security Standards to enforce a limited set of privileges on containers. This protects the host operating system and hardware (for example storage or networking) from being attacked by malicious users or compromised code in the TRE.

We also shared our approach to securing the Kubernetes network through using a modern Container Network Interface (CNI). The technique is to block all network traffic by default and selectively allow only the network traffic that is essential for the operation of the TRE. Using a CNI is a scalable solution, which allows us to write Kubernetes-native networking rules taking advantage of the taxonomy of Kubernetes objects. Together, these network and container security improvements added an additional layer to the “defence in depth” security approach taken by both FRIDGE and K8TRE.

The DIRECTOR project is building a range of Kubernetes applications for federated TREs. We worked less closely with DIRECTOR but, similarly to K8TRE, we aimed to ensure the long-term compatibility of our outputs and prevent duplicated effort. Most significantly, we avoided developing a production-ready method

for connecting a TRE to its FRIDGE instance(s) and instead planned for the future integration of DIRECTOR MESH, which represents a generalisation of connecting federated TREs that could become common across TRevolution and the wider DARE products.

2.3. Reflections and feedback

A number of projects across DARE have aligned on building trusted research tools on top of a Kubernetes base. This coalescence of approach made for productive collaboration and exchange of ideas between projects. We were clear on the value of choosing Kubernetes as a common platform, which enables components to be easily shared and deployed into any Kubernetes-supporting TRE. Furthermore it keeps open the potential for tools to be collected together, or even integrated, in the future.

Collaboration and discussion between Phase 2 projects established a shared understanding of the medium-to-long term potential of the tools we were building. Importantly, we were able to align on the broader, high-level challenges in compatibility without needing to understand or contribute to the low-level details of other projects. Compared to the Phase 1 Driver and Sprint projects, the Phase 2 outputs are closer to a cohesive whole of modular, compatible TRE tools.

An example of the forward-thinking goals the collaboration enabled is the potential for the FRIDGE TRE Tenancy to become the secure container for the entire ecosystem of modular TRevolution components. Such a development would allow all TRevolution tools to benefit from the extra layer of security the TRE Tenancy provides in situations where it is required. This could also potentially provide a way to easily deploy TRevolution components alongside existing TREs, and unlocks options for building TREs such as K8TRE in a TRE Tenancy deployed to HPC.

There were however some missed opportunities for more effective collaboration. Despite many tools being developed as Kubernetes applications (or collections of applications), there is not yet one agreed approach to the distribution of components. One aspect of the DIRECTOR project is to manage the deployment and compliance of TRE components. This approach expands on continuous deployment of Helm charts. To take full advantage of DIRECTOR as the distribution platform for TRE components, each will need to meet the requirements for inclusion as a “DIRECTOR app”. FRIDGE development took a different approach with Kubernetes resources defined declaratively alongside cloud infrastructure in Infrastructure as Code. This may limit the possibility for FRIDGE to be deployed by DIRECTOR, or at least require extra development to realign.

Another DIRECTOR product is DIRECTOR-MESH, a tool and approach to selectively and securely connecting the networks of federated TREs. This could be considered a generalisation of the challenge in FRIDGE of connecting a TRE to the FRIDGE satellite TRE. Being aware of each other’s work helped ensure we did not build competing functions and the expectation for FRIDGE is to incorporate DIRECTOR-MESH in the future. However, at the conclusion of FRIDGE DIRECTOR-MESH has not been implemented and so it has not been validated as part of a FRIDGE deployment. Better communication between DIRECTOR and FRIDGE could have helped express the important role we imagine DIRECTOR-MESH playing for FRIDGE and could have adjusted priorities in a way that we could have worked together to implement and test this earlier.

FRIDGE and Five Safes TES missed an opportunity to align on the tools and language used for workflow management. Both projects handle the dispatching of jobs to remote compute resources. For FRIDGE, this is the very narrow case of a job being sent to remote infrastructure, which still falls under the same TRE

governance. Five Safes TES tackles are different, more general use case, where jobs are sent from one TRE to run on another TRE. As such, Five Safes TES must handle metadata outlining governance rules of a federation and ensure that a proposed job is properly approved before it can run. It could be possible that job dispatch in the FRIDGE context is just a special case, where the approval process is simplified to account for the job not crossing TRE boundaries.

The FRIDGE job manager is Argo Workflows, whereas Five Safes TES expands on the GA4GH TES standard. This difference prevents the simple addition of FRIDGE instances as Five Safes TES clients, and extra work would be required for jobs in a Five Safes TES federation to be dispatched to FRIDGE. Furthermore, this choice is a blocker to exploring FRIDGE as a special case of Five Safes TES and sharing core components. As it stands, there are two DARE outputs using different, and incompatible job execution services.

3. The Early Adopter process

3.1. What worked well

Overall, we found engaging with the Early Adopter workstream a very positive experience and felt that the DARE UK Phase 2 programme overall took a very good approach in structuring the work it funded. It balanced a co-ordinated approach to further development of the tools and methods identified in Phase 1 with supporting wider community involvement both with that core work and with filling remaining gaps in capability and adoption. The combination of a stable, coherent, tightly integrated core TREvolution workstream and more targeted supporting work through the Early Adopters, Real-world Research Exemplars and Next-Gen Catalyst programmes was very powerful. Critically these additional workstreams were flexible enough to support a diverse set of activities that augmented the core TREvolution programme in different ways and funded at a level that supported meaningful level of contribution from multiple organisations per project. Together with the efforts from the core DARE UK team to connect these projects with the core TREvolution team, the result was a very coherent overall programme of work, involving a significant and diverse set of organisations from the TRE community, that has become significantly more than the sum of its parts.

3.2. Challenges encountered

3.2.1. Duration and timing of projects

We found the 12-month duration of the Early Adopter projects challenging for getting to the point of validating the FRIDGE approach in a fully representative real-world context across the TRE and supercomputer systems, especially on the information governance front. Part of this was us being particularly ambitious in our goals, but more generally we think that it is extremely challenging to validate TRE innovations that are not already “production level” in a genuinely representative real-world TRE technical and governance context in a 12-month timeframe.

While the Early Adopter call was realistic in its expectations that evaluation would almost certainly be done with non-sensitive synthetic data, this meant that the data and project use cases did not provide the same strength of “forcing function” to resolve the full complexity of bridging the production governance processes at Turing and AIRR. Similarly, while the FRIDGE implementation was not expected to be more than a proof-of-concept demonstration, the fact it was not production-ready also meant that some of the more complex

real-world reality of bridging information governance across two organisations was not forced onto the “critical path”.

The strong overlap between the timings of the core TRevolution workstream developing the new TRE components and the Early Adopter projects adopting and evaluating them meant that, in practice the Early Adopter projects were mostly working with TRevolution components at the proof-of-concept demonstrator level achieved in Phase 1 of the DARE programme. The fact that FRIDGE and some other Early Adopter projects started 3 months before the main TRevolution workstream exacerbated this further. FRIDGE also needed components that were not yet developed by TRevolution so had to independently develop these where needed.

We welcome the addition of the Real-world Research Exemplar workstream targeted at evaluating the TRevolution capabilities in production TRE settings. This feels like a very natural next step from the Early Adopter workstream and is a great example of the DARE programme shaping itself to best support the maturation of the TRE components it's developing and the wider community in evaluating these and feeding into their iterative development.

3.2.2. Integration and collaboration

It took some time for the Early Adopter projects to feel integrated with the core TRevolution teams, though this sense of integration did emerge over time, thanks to a series of co-ordinating events organised by the DARE programme. The time for the Early Adopter and TRevolution workstreams to feel genuinely part of a co-ordinated whole was likely largely down to the time taken for the core TRevolution teams to integrate across their own workstreams and the fact that Early Adopters were largely working with the outputs of DARE Phase 1 while the TRevolution core teams were working on developing these further in Phase 2.

FRIDGE took a pro-active approach in co-ordinating with the TRevolution core teams, having identified K8TRE and DIRECTOR as key workstreams with strong overlap in terms of the challenges we were addressing. Collaboration with the K8TRE team was strong from the start, with the teams working together to co-design the TRE tenancy model and its common Kubernetes-based infrastructure layer. The FRIDGE team contributed much of the security elements of the tenancy, driven by the additional complexity of our use case that involved the tenancy and the TRE being deployed by two different organisations. The eventual goal is for the same TRE tenancy to be able to support deployment of any TRevolution component within it, whether within a FRIDGE satellite TRE or a K8TRE “full stack” TRE.

FRIDGE engaged with the DIRECTOR team early on, but it took several months before this engagement was truly meaningful in terms of having a clear view of and influencing each other's design and development work. This was largely due to the DIRECTOR team needing some time to define their initial core Phase 2 approach. Once this was defined, collaboration was much more productive, with the involvement of the FRIDGE and DIRECTOR teams in the TETREs TRE test network acting as a force multiplier for this by allowing us to evaluate some of the key DIRECTOR components in collaboration with several other TRE operators. FRIDGE also leveraged the fact DIRECTOR was working on core secure networking capabilities for TRE federations to implement a minimal viable solution to this for our proof-of-concept demonstrator, with the plan being to adopt the DIRECTOR mesh networking component when it is ready.

The potential alignment of the FRIDGE satellite TRE workload management component with the Five Safes TES workstream did not become apparent until nearer the end of the project. FRIDGE and Five Safes TES have initially focussed on different aspects of the workload distribution and execution pipeline. The FRIDGE

workload manager focusses on providing a simple workload submission API and workload runner on the satellite TRE, exposing this API directly within the linked home TRE, with all elements controlled by the same organisation. The Five Safe TES component has initially focussed on providing a common workload description model for passing workloads between federated TRE systems run by different organisations, with a central distribution hub. However, there are clear areas of potential alignment, and we will look to explore these as we further develop FRIDGE from proof-of-concept to production-ready implementation.

While the sense of integration and collaboration between the Early Adopter and TRevolution teams grew in strength over time to form a truly coherent collection of workstreams, there did not appear to be similarly strong collaboration across Early Adopter projects beyond sharing experiences at the DARE organised events. It is however possible that other Early Adopters experienced this type of collaboration more strongly. As FRIDGE was developing additional components for the TRevolution ecosystem, our collaboration was naturally more directed to the core TRevolution team.

Integration of PIE activities took longer to establish than we expected, largely due to the time taken to establish the core TRevolution PIE group. However, in general FRIDGE PIE activity was as well integrated into the wider DARE PIE activity as we could have hoped. We engaged strongly with the DARE Collaboration Cafe series, including hosting our own FRIDGE-focussed cafe, and took part in one of the wider DARE AI Dialogue workshops. Our PIE lead was also PIE co-lead for the core TRevolution workstream and ensured that key FRIDGE concerns were appropriately considered by that workstream and we took advantage of the work of the core TRevolution PIE workstream on areas of common concern. That said, we found there was a limit to the depth we could go into on the key FRIDGE-focussed concerns with PIE groups external to the project and this was a key motivator in establishing the project-focussed TRE PIE group at Turing.

Working within the DARE community presents a lot of opportunity for collaboration, and the coordination within and between programs promotes the force-multiplying effect of projects aligning, ensuring the whole is larger than the sum of its parts. For FRIDGE there were clear opportunities for integration. Being more development/product focused than other early adopters, the team was eager to ensure FRIDGE became one of a compatible set of modular TRevolution tools.

Keeping track of the work happening across all relevant DARE programs was difficult, exacerbated by the staggered project timelines and starting ahead of TRevolution. On reflection, more effort spent synchronising with other DARE projects could have helped DARE products be more coherent and reduce duplication of effort. A more centralised was to set objectives across all projects, putting more emphasis on integration could keep the management burden on individual projects low while maximising coordination. Although the end results could have been more tightly integrated, we feel the collaboration was sufficient to avoid any significant incompatibility, and we recognise that bringing these tools to production is an ongoing process.

3.3. Recommendations for Improvement

Overall, we feel the structure of the DARE programme is excellent. The combination of a core, integrated development workstream with more diverse, community-driven Early Adopter and Real-world Research Exemplar workstreams to support evaluation and adoption is extremely powerful and well-matched to the task of iteratively developing TRE capabilities shaped by the community and supporting their adoption. The combination of early adopters shaping these capabilities while they are still being developed and real-world exemplars evaluating the capabilities in more production contexts when they are more mature is a powerful combination. The inclusion of the Next-Gen Catalyst workstream to support the exploration and initial proof-

of-concept development of the next set of TRE capabilities is also a very strong addition that means the programme is not operating in a “boom and bust” model, but instead setting up a more continual “conveyor belt” from the innovation frontier to production deployment.

However, the DARE UK Phase 2 programme would have strongly benefitted from a significantly longer duration of 4-5 years, with the Early Adopter workstream kicking off in year 3, once the core TRevolution components had hit a more mature “minimal viable product” level for deployment and evaluation in a production TRE context. While there is a balance to be struck between early feedback to steer product development and maturity of the components being evaluated, having components closer to “feature complete” for at least core features would support evaluations in more realistic environments and, in the ideal world, could result in components reaching the threshold for actual production deployment at Early Adopter TREs following 12-months of evaluation, feedback and co-design with the core TRevolution teams.

Having all or most TRevolution components deployed in production at least one TRE site at the end of the Early Adopter workstream would also provide a stronger foundation for the Real-world Research Exemplar workstream to focus on genuine production deployments supporting real-world research with real sensitive data. Given the current state of development of some of the TRevolution components, it is not guaranteed that all Real-world Research Exemplars will manage to get to the point where they are comfortable leveraging them in their production TRE environments for research with real sensitive data. Therefore, it is not guaranteed that all TRevolution capabilities will be deployed and evaluated in a genuine production use case.

Having an initial year of development by the core TRevolution programme would also have helped with this core team fully integrating before the early adopters were brought into the fold, making it easier for them to integrate into the programme. Launching the Early Adopter workstream one year into the core TRevolution workstream may also have attracted a wider range of early adopter organisations, through a combination of being able to evaluate more feature complete capabilities and having had more time to engage with the core TRevolution workstream prior to the Early Adopter call.

All that said, given the realities of the 2-year timeline for the overall Phase 2 programme, we feel the DARE team did an excellent job of putting together an integrated programme of work to support the development of key TRE capabilities and their adoption by the community. Despite the challenges of overlap in timings, the combination of the core TRevolution programme and the Early Adopter, Real-world Research Exemplar and Next-Gen Catalyst workstreams provide a well-balanced and well-integrated portfolio of work that together establish a powerful innovation-to-impact pathway for identifying and developing new TRE capabilities and supporting the development of proven capabilities to the point at which they can be deployed and evaluated in a production context. As DARE and UKRI consider what a potential DARE Phase 3 programme would look like, we would encourage them to retain and refine this “conveyor belt” while extending this to cover the final push from “validated in production” to “business as usual” production service. We would also strongly advocate for longer-term stability in terms of funding and road map for any Phase 3 programme, with a target duration of 4-5 years.

Accepting the overarching constraints of the current DARE Phase 2 programme, we would recommend DARE continue the excellent work they have been doing convening the projects in the various workstreams together into a wider coherent community. This activity has been invaluable in making the various workstreams more than the sum of their parts and we would recommend DARE continue to review and improve this activity as they have done over the course of the Early Adopter projects. For new projects joining one of the DARE workstreams we would strongly encourage them to enthusiastically engage with the

DARE organised cohort events as well as to reach out early to the core TRevolution teams for the components they are adopting to ensure they can gain a deeper understanding of their development roadmaps and establish regular meet ups and effective communication channels. We would also recommend they reach out to other projects within their workstream where there are overlaps in the TRevolution components they are adopting.

4. Public Involvement and Engagement

4.1. Approach

Our PIE lead was also a co-lead and PIE lead for the core TRevolution workstream, which has established its own PIE group. The health research project at the Turing we were working with was also establishing its own PIE group. Our original expectation was that we would be able to work with these two PIE groups to ensure that our engagement activity was integrated with the main TRevolution workstream and this real-world research project. However, both these PIE groups took time to set up, only becoming established around 10 months into the FRIDGE project. We also found that, while engaging with PIE groups external to the project was useful, we struggled to get the depth of engagement we wanted for some of the aspects that were most important to our work. We therefore augmented these groups by establishing a TRE Public Advisory Group at Turing, setting this up in the last few months of the project. This group was scoped to support the set of DARE UK funded projects Turing has been leading, to take advantage of the common background and overlap in context between them. We have found this combination of a core PIE group “embedded” in the project work and engagement with wider PIE activity within the DARE programme a highly effective combination for being able to get both the depth and breadth of public input we need.

In the end, our PIE programme consisted of a mix of core PIE work within the project and strong engagement with wider PIE activity across the DARE UK programme.

4.1.1. Core project embedded PIE activity

The embedding of PIE across the project started with the project leadership structure. Our PIE lead was a full-fledged member of the project leadership team and a formal co-investigator on the project. They were supported by our principal investigator as PIE co-lead and joined them at all DARE events to represent the project. This embedding of PIE into top-level project leadership set expectations across the project team that the public perspective needed to be embedded into all aspects of the project, and ensure that everyone on the team prioritised supporting our more structured PIE activity. From the start of the project, our PIE lead worked with the project team to upskill them in how to embed the public perspective into their day to day thinking and to effectively engage with the public at PIE events. This built on previous experience of collaboration between our PIE lead, other co-leads and team members on the DARE Phase 1 SATRE project. Team members were active participants in a range of DARE Collaboration Cafes and the full project team was involved in delivering a dedicated FRIDGE Collaboration Cafe in November 2026.

About 6 months into the project, we identified the lack of a core project-focussed PIE group as a key weakness and worked to establish the Turing’s TRE Public Advisory Group (PAG) to provide this support. 10 public members were recruited from across the UK, with almost all members new to working with research projects. Members were recruited from a range of different community groups to create a group with a good

gender and ethnicity mix and with diverse backgrounds, including members for whom English is not their first language. The first meeting of this group was a full-day workshop in mid-December 2026 and we have since established a cadence of quarterly in-person workshops, augmented by monthly online sessions between these. Pooling PIE resources across related DARE funded projects has been extremely powerful in enabling us to support a level of both depth and frequency of engagement from this group to enable them to genuinely shape the work of these projects on a month-to-month basis.

In addition to the regular online meetings and in-person workshops, we are running a regular structured survey with our PAG to capture the evolution of their understanding and viewpoints over the course of these projects, as well as formally capturing any concerns arising as the projects progress. These are critical to ensuring that we remain in tune with our PAG members and continually validate our understanding of their views and concerns. We also have a more informal WhatsApp group where the PIE lead and members can discuss issues more fluidly as they arise and to provide a space for the group to discuss things amongst themselves outside the structures of the regular meetings and workshops. This has been effective at both capturing more open, informal feedback from the PAG after working sessions and for capturing emerging concerns such as those raised by the recent news about UK Biobank data incidents.

4.1.2. Engagement with wider DARE UK PIE activity

Our PIE lead was involved in a range of wider PIE activity across the DARE programme, leveraging his role as PIE lead within the TREvolution workstream. The FRIDGE project team was represented at most of the DARE UK Collaboration Cafes, with around half of these cafes chaired by our PIE lead in his role as PIE lead for the core TREvolution workstream. We worked with the core TREvolution PIE team to ensure that key questions and concerns for the FRIDGE project were integrated into relevant Collaboration Cafe and PIE group discussion sessions and that we had appropriate FRIDGE team engagement for these and other discussion sessions where our work connected with that of the core TREvolution workstream. As mentioned above, we also ran a dedicated FRIDGE-focussed Collaboration Cafe, which was extremely useful in gathering the views of a wide range of public participants.

We had a very positive meeting with the DARE UK AI Dialogue group in Birmingham, with the FRIDGE research and PIE leads presenting on FRIDGE and engaging with the full day's discussion groups. We learned that the public know that research is important and that AI has its place but also that there were widespread concerns about the broader role of AI in society and that consent for its use in research was conditional on the existence of appropriate safeguards. At this event we also learned how best to communicate with the public. This is for the team to come up with the presentation but for the PIE lead to deliver the presentation, with support from the team when questions come up that are out of the PIE leads skillset. We adopted this approach for the FRIDGE Collaboration Cafe and other public-focussed events. This approach was also very effective in onboarding the Turing TRE PAG members to the project. Learning to present and translate the work to the public has been really helpful for such a technical project, and we continue to learn, with more and more team members gaining experience of presenting to and running discussion sessions with public participants.

4.2. Findings

When we were originally planning the FRIDGE PIE workstream, we expected the public's concerns would be around two broad areas: the risk of using parts of a computer system controlled by someone else for sensitive data, and concerns around the effect of being able to apply AI methods to much larger sensitive datasets

through access to the AI supercomputers. While these were the two main areas of concerns related to the work we were doing in FRIDGE to extend TREs to supercomputers, we also found that there is a big background concern about the broader use of AI in society, especially by commercial entities, and we spent quite some time with our project-focussed PAG on this topic and the wider question of which organisations should be trusted with sensitive data and what safeguards need to be in place for different types of organisation. This more general concern about the use of AI in society and which organisations should be trusted with sensitive data was also a central topic of discussion at the DARE UK AI Dialogue group session we attended in Birmingham. Overall, several themes emerged from our discussions across the different strands of our PIE activity, which we summarise briefly below.

4.2.1. Which organisations are trustworthy?

Different types of organisation engendered different levels of trust with the public. There was a general distrust of commercial organisations, especially those related to AI and those perceived as “big tech” more generally. The NHS and universities were generally highly trusted, but trust in government more broadly was much more varied, with some concerns about government “snooping” and potential collaboration between big tech and police and intelligence services. Overall, there was a general fear of the motivations of commercial organisations, especially free services where the “user is the product” and generating a personal user profile is an explicit goal for targeting ads. This concern about “big tech” organisations spilled over to concerns about hosting TREs in public clouds run by the likes of Microsoft, Amazon and Google, despite many operational research TREs being hosted on these platforms, and there was also a general wariness about storing sensitive data outside of the UK. There was a nuanced discussion about different types and levels of trust, from trusting an organisation for a short period to time to e.g. do data linkage, to trusting an organisation to trust others on our behalf, with being able to establish the trust chain or provenance of trust a key consideration. There were also concerns about trust changing over time, for example as legal frameworks for data protection or societal norms change and the challenges of the public being able to provide genuinely informed societal consent when the pace of technological change is so fast moving, especially in AI. This concern around informed consent included a strong desire for transparency about what data is used for, with the principle that the public should not be surprised by any use of their data key.

4.2.2. General concerns about AI in society

The public groups we talked to generally recognised the benefits of AI in many areas. However, there were concerns about ensuring that AI use is ethical, the use of copyrighted material in training AI models, the potential of AI to exacerbate biases and other societal inequities, and the potential impact on jobs. Overall the public felt they lacked a clear understanding of how AI worked and therefore has insufficient insight to be able to meaningfully evaluate its risks vs its potential benefits. They also felt that the pace of development in AI was so fast that it felt almost impossible to keep up with it sufficiently to make informed judgements on its use. There were concerns about the accuracy of AI methods, the risk of too much trust being placed in AI, lack of effective human oversight, and the privacy of data when used with AI. Concerns about use of AI initially extended to the use of AI for research. These concerns generally eased substantially following discussions about the difference between the types of AI methods used in research vs more consumer-oriented AI like ChatGPT, as well as the additional ethical, information governance and data security controls in place for the use of AI and sensitive data in research. However, some concerns remained around risks of trusting AI too much, including the use of AI for autonomous research.

4.2.3. Environmental impact of AI

Concerns about the environmental impact of AI datacentres and supercomputers was a common theme, including carbon emissions associated with electricity generation, cooling and the manufacturing of datacentres and the computers within them. There was enthusiasm for the use of renewable energy to power data centres and for reusing waste heat from data centre cooling for home heating. However, there was also recognition that the increase in energy demand from AI data centres exceeded the capacity of new clean energy generation capacity, so AI would likely result in increased total emissions, regardless of the type of energy generation used to power any particular data centre. There was also interest in the use of some types of AI to reduce the amount of compute needed for research, such as the use of “emulators” to substitute for more energy intensive simulations.

4.2.4. Safe use of data in research

Our project-focussed PIE group was generally unfamiliar with research and did not have much prior understanding or awareness of the type of data used for research and how this data is protected. We therefore spent some of our initial conversations on more general concerns about the safe use of sensitive data in research. The group was greatly reassured by the ethical, information governance and security controls used to protect sensitive data used for research, including the Five Safes principles and the use of TREs to limit access to data to approved researchers for approved projects. However, some concerns remained in this area, with the overarching residual concern being around transparency about what is being done with data and who makes decisions about how it is used and where it is processed. These felt very much in line with the eighth Caldicott Principle of “no surprises”. Patients wanted to ensure that use of their data was aligned not just to legal principles, but also to common expectations of privacy. They felt that it was difficult for them to get an overall view of what research their data was being used for and by whom, as well as to understand how decisions were made on where data is processed and on trade-offs between the benefits of using data for research vs risks to privacy. The group wanted to understand how levels of protection were tuned to the sensitivity level of different data sets and how the risk of bringing large data sets together was managed. While trust in research organisations was generally high, the group wanted to understand how TREs and organisations working with sensitive data were audited as part of a “trust but verify” approach, as well as wanting to understand the dependencies for the different types of controls protecting their data on technical, legal and societal underpinnings. These last points on auditing and dependencies were ones that were particularly strongly felt when considering the FRIDGE shared responsibility model and other cases where multiple organisations need to work together effectively to ensure the safety of the data.

4.2.5. How we explain our work

The group struggled with the amount of jargon involved in the project and the wider TRE landscape. They also found that some of the explanations of the more complex technical and governance aspects of FRIDGE were initially not communicated clearly enough for them to fully understand them. This was also true for some aspects of the wider TRE landscape. The group found the Five Safes model very useful for anchoring their understanding of where different controls contributed to safety and security within both FRIDGE and the wider TRE model. The group also wanted a clearer understanding of the underlying legal frameworks underpinning the safe use of sensitive data for research.

4.3. Impact and learnings

In terms of how we develop FRIDGE, the biggest impact of engaging with PIE groups has been the embedding of the public perspective more deeply within the team's day-to-day work. Hearing directly from the public above their concerns and being able to discuss these with them in detail has really strengthened our understanding of these concerns and what they are rooted in. It has also made us much more self-aware that our own perspectives as people deeply embedded in the TRE landscape are not representative of the wider public and to ensure we are considering the public's perspective in our day-to-day decision making. The team have also become much better at communicating what FRIDGE is, both to the public and to others outside the project, including the other DARE projects, funders and stakeholders in the TRE and supercomputer communities.

In terms of how we do PIE, the key impact of our PIE experience has been the establishment of a Turing TRE Public Advisory Group to act as a project-focussed PIE group for FRIDGE and related projects. This was partially driven by the time taken to stand up the PIE teams we expected to work with within the wider DARE programme and the demonstrator project we were working with at Turing. However, it was mainly due to us not being able to get into the depth we needed to with these external PIE groups. Establishing a project-focussed PIE group allowed us to embed these public members more deeply in our work and give them the background to provide truly informed input and steer our work from within. The flexibility provided by DARE to pool resources for funding this group across related projects has allowed us to more deeply embed this group in our DARE funded work, with quarterly full day in-person workshops and monthly online half day meetings in between these.

A key insight for us from working with both our PIE group and engaging in wider DARE PIE activity has been that making things clear for those with the least shared context makes our explanations more useful for almost everybody. On occasion we have even found ourselves revisiting our own conceptualisation of something after we have struggled to explain it to our public members. We have taken this approach further, with the team co-creating analogies and visualisations with the PIE group, and our PIE lead being the primary presenter at for presentations targeted at the wider public. We have also realised that every group who is not already familiar with the wider TRE landscape needs a good grounding in this wider landscape to be able to provide genuinely informed input into the specific work a project is doing within this landscape. We found ourselves going much more deeply into the foundations of how sensitive data is used in research and how it is protected than we had initially expected to but we have reaped the rewards of this with much deeper and insightful engagement from our PIE group. Being able to amortise this initial deep onboarding by having a single PIE group across related projects has been key to enabling this.

5. Conclusions and future directions

5.1 Key conclusions

5.1.1. The FRIDGE project

We have validated the FRIDGE satellite TRE model on the two AIRR national AI supercomputers. We have shown that a secure TRE tenancy with a common Kubernetes-based infrastructure layer can be established across the two AIRR systems and Microsoft's Azure public cloud platform, with a clean separation between the system-specific TRE tenancy implementation on each host platform and the common satellite TRE

components deployed within these tenancies. We have also shown that the shared responsibility model works in principle, though operationalising this on AIRR will involve more complexity than originally anticipated due to DSIT's role as the overarching resource allocator across the two AIRR systems. We have had significant interest in the FRIDGE approach from both TRE and supercomputer operators, and we plan to continue the development of FRIDGE from proof-of-concept to production-ready implementation over the coming year. In particular, the NHS Secure Data Environment (SDE) network is keen to leverage the FRIDGE model to extend its SDEs onto satellite TREs on supercomputers hosted at university partners.

Having a PIE group focussed on FRIDGE and related work has been extremely powerful for being able to dive deep into the topics most relevant to our work, as well as more deeply embedding the public perspective across the project's activities and steering its direction on a month-to-month basis. Being able to pool resources across these related projects with common core background context and common areas of concern has allowed us to support much deeper and more regular public engagement with the work and we would encourage this as an approach for other projects where work is closely related.

5.1.2. Collaboration across the DARE programme

While it took some time to get going, DARE have done an excellent job of convening the various projects across their workstreams into a coherent wider collaborative community that is significantly greater than the sum of its parts. The combination of DARE organised events and deeper collaborative design and evaluation sessions with the core TRevolution teams have been extremely helpful in integrating the Early Adopters with the core TRevolution workstream. The team will continue to engage with the core TRevolution team as we develop FRIDGE further.

The Collaboration Cafe model has been extremely useful to incorporate a broader range of public perspectives and validate our approaches with a wider audience. These should continue to be part of the regular DARE supported PIE activity, and all DARE projects should be strongly encouraged to engage with these. The DARE UK AI Dialogue workstream was also a great way to do a deeper dive with public participants not already involved with the DARE programme and to hear from under-represented communities. We would encourage other activities like this as part of the overall DARE PIE workstream. One potential additional strand to this wider engagement activity could be a DARE programme "road show", presenting to and getting the perspective of various under-represented communities.

5.2. Future use of TRevolution capabilities

We will continue to develop FRIDGE from proof-of-concept to a production-ready implementation, working with an expanded team of collaborators to validate the FRIDGE approach with an additional TRE provider and make three high impact health datasets available on AIRR for three real-world exemplar projects. As we do so, we will continue to engage with the core TRevolution workstream to ensure that we are not duplicating efforts and are developing complementary components within the TRevolution ecosystem. In particular, we will work closely with:

- SATE to ensure that the FRIDGE satellite TRE model continues to remain SATE compliant as the v2.0 specification is finalised and to continue to inform the new federation pillar.
- K8TRE to ensure that we evolve the FRIDGE TRE tenancy into a common approach for securing the underlying platform a TRE is deployed onto, whether a FRIDGE "satellite" TRE or a K8TRE "full stack" TRE.

- DIRECTOR to adopt their secure mesh networking component for connecting between home TREs and the FRIDGE satellite TREs deployed on the supercomputers.
- Five Safes TES to explore whether we can converge on a single approach for end-to-end workload submission, transmission and execution across federated systems.
- SACRO-ML to evaluate their semi-automated approaches for determining whether AI whether AI models and their outputs can be safely egressed from a TRE.

5.3. Support needed for expanded use

The core of our work to take FRIDGE from proof-of-concept to production-ready is funded through a DARE Real-world Research Exemplar grant, we will need continued close engagement from the core TRevolution team to ensure that we can effectively leverage the components they are developing as they also reach production-readiness.

However, we would benefit from additional DARE support to help expand the impact scope of this work to a wider set of TRE operators, supercomputer operators, data providers and researchers. We would like to be able to provide more in-depth hands-on support to organisations outside our Real-world Research Exemplar collaboration in either leveraging FRIDGE to support research with sensitive data on AIRR or to evaluate and adopt the FRIDGE model in their own contexts. In particular, we would like to be able to provide hands-on support for any NHS SDE consortia who would like to trial FRIDGE for extending their SDE to both AIRR and to supercomputers at their local university partners. Enabling access to large scale AI-enabled compute capability for the NHS SDEs would represent a high-impact use case in and of itself but, coupled with the launch of the Health Data Research Service, there is a real opportunity to leverage three national-scale investments in digital research infrastructure across DARE, AIRR and the HDRS.